

Stability Constants of Some Carboxylate Complexes of Plutonium(III) and Samarium(III)

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The stability constants of the complexes formed by plutonium(III) and samarium(III) with formate, acetate and propionate ions were determined by the Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration method at 25° in 1M NaClO₄ medium. The values were calculated by a weighted least squares method ignoring the hydrolysis of the metal ion and also incorporating a correction for the hydrolysis. The results obtained indicated that the hydrolysis correction was significant in the case of plutonium(III) complexes.

THE stability constants of plutonium(III) complexes with carboxylate ions like formate, acetate and propionate are of interest since some of these reagents are used as back washing agents during the amine extraction of plutonium in the purification step^{1,2}. The corresponding values for samarium(III) [which is the lanthanide homologue of plutonium(III)] are useful for comparison purpose. A few values are available in literature on the stability constants of plutonium(III)-acetate^{3,4} and samarium(III)-acetate and propionate^{5,6} complexes which were determined by potentiometric method. However, no attempt has been made by the earlier authors to correct the stability constant values for the hydrolysis of the metal ions. Therefore it was considered worthwhile to determine the stability constants of the complexes formed by plutonium(III) and samarium(III) with formate, acetate and propionate ions after taking into consideration the hydrolysis of the metal ions under the experimental conditions. Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique was used for the study^{7,8}. The experiments were carried out in 1M NaClO₄ medium at 25°.

Experimental

Reagents: Plutonium used in the experiments was purified by anion exchange and peroxide precipitation steps⁹. Plutonium(IV) solution finally obtained in 1M HClO₄ medium was electrolytically reduced to get plutonium(III) which was estimated both by controlled potential coulometry¹⁰ and by potentiometric titration¹¹. Samarium(III) in HClO₄ medium was prepared starting from 99.9% pure Sm(NO₃)₃ supplied by M/s. Indian Rare Earths Ltd. It was estimated by EDTA titration using xylenol orange as the indicator¹².

The ligands formic, acetic and propionic acids were distilled from AR products. They were either used directly or as solutions in 1M NaClO₄ medium. Sodium perchlorate and carbonate free sodium hydroxide solutions were prepared, standardised and stored as described elsewhere^{13,14}. Hydroiodic acid solutions used were prepared fresh every time by mixing equal

volumes of 2M KI and 2M HClO₄ and removing the KClO₄ precipitate formed. Deaerated double distilled water was used for preparation of all solutions.

Apparatus: A cell as shown in Fig. 1 was used for the titrations. The electrodes (glass electrode and calomel), the thermometer, the gas passing tube and the burette tip were introduced through the holes in the teflon stopper of the cell. A Beckman Research Model

Fig. 1. Titration Cell: 1. Outer jacket; 2. Titration vessel; 3. Teflon stopper; 4. Nitrogen inlet; 5. Glass electrode; 6. Thermometer; 7. Reference electrode; 8. Burette tip; 9. NaCl bridge; 10. Stirring bar and 11. B-54 Standard joint.

pH meter was used for all pH measurements. This was used in conjunction with a blue bulb Beckman E2 type glass electrode having low sodium error and BR72 special type saturated calomel electrode from M/s.

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Elico Pvt. Ltd. The calomel electrode was introduced through a bridge tube containing 1M NaCl to prevent the formation of $KClO_4$ at the fibre tip. The pH meter was calibrated to get the hydrogen ion concentration from the measured pH.

Titration: pH titrations were carried out by adding known volumes of standard NaOH to a solution containing the metal ion and the ligand in known concentration ratios. Argon was passed through the solution to deaerate the solution and to keep an inert atmosphere over the same. The pH reading was noted after the addition of each aliquot of the titrant. The titration was stopped when the system became opalescent due to the precipitation of the metal as its hydrolysis and or complex products. For determination of the dissociation constants of the ligands, these experiments were conducted in the absence of the metal ions. In systems involving Pu(III), a concentration of 0.1M HI was maintained at the beginning of the experiment in order to prevent the oxidation of plutonium(III) to plutonium(IV).

Calculations: The stability constants are calculated as follows by weighted least squares from the formation function \bar{n} ⁷ (the average number of ligands attached to each metal ion). From the dissociable hydrogen balance equation¹⁸, the experimental \bar{n} value is obtained as follows:

$$\bar{n} = \frac{[T_L] - [C_L]}{[T_M]} \quad \dots (1)$$

where $[T_L]$ is the total ligand concentration, $[C_L]$ is the concentration of unbound ligand and $[T_M]$ is the total metal concentration.

For a system containing two complexes ML and ML_2 with the overall stability constants β_1 and β_2 respectively,

$$\bar{n} = \frac{\beta_1 [L] + 2 \beta_2 [L]^2}{1 + \beta_1 [L] + \beta_2 [L]^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

where $[L]$ is the free ligand ion concentration. (Charges on the species in the above equation and those to follow are omitted for convenience). From equations (1) and (2) the following equation can be arrived at

$$\sum_{n=0}^2 \{ [T_L] - [C_L] - n[T_M] \} \beta_n [L]^n = U \quad \dots (3)$$

where U represents the error in the measurements.

The error sum of squares S for m experimental points is given by

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^m U_i^2$$

If a weight W_i is associated with each experimental point, the error sum of squares becomes

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^m W_i U_i^2 \quad \dots (4)$$

The above equation can be solved for the parameters β_1 and β_2 by the method of least squares.

The weight of each point is calculated as follows¹⁵:

$$W = \frac{1}{(\delta U)^2}$$

where $\delta U = \frac{dU}{d[H]} \sigma_H$

In the above equation, the value of σ_H is the uncertainty in the hydrogen ion measurement, taken to be equal to 0.01 pH unit.

The above calculations were done in iterative steps with the help of the computer BESM-6, calculating weights each time using values from the previous step until consistent values of the stability constants were obtained. Three to five iterations were necessary to get consistent values.

The calculation steps given above assume the absence of any hydrolysis of the metal ion or the complex species formed. However, considering the hydrolysis constant values of the metal ions determined¹⁶ and the pH of the solutions during the titrations, it was considered worthwhile to correct for the hydrolysis of the metal ions in the calculation of the stability constants of the complexes formed. It was assumed that under the conditions of the experiment, the complexes formed did not undergo any hydrolysis.

The hydrolysis correction was carried out by the following steps: For a system containing two complex species ML and ML_2 and the hydrolysis species $M(OH)$, $M(OH)_2$, $M(OH)_n$ (polynuclear species were considered to be not formed in the system)

$$[T_M] = [M] + [ML] + [ML_2] + \sum_{n=1}^N [M(OH)_n] \quad \dots (5)$$

Equation (5) can be rewritten in terms of the stability constants of the complexes β_1 and β_2 and the hydrolysis constants:

$$[T_M] = [M] (1 + \beta_1 [L] + \beta_2 [L]^2 + \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\beta_n^h}{[H]^n})$$

where, $\beta_n^h = \frac{[M(OH)_n] [H]^n}{[M]}$

From the values of β_1 and β_2 obtained from calculations ignoring hydrolysis, and the known values of

the hydrolysis constants¹⁶, the first value of [M] can be computed.

Knowing the value of [M], the concentration of the hydrolysis species $\sum_{n=1}^N [M(OH)_n]$ is obtained and therefrom the concentration of the hydrogen ion, $[H_h]$ liberated due to the hydrolysis of the metal ion.

$$[H_h] = n \sum_{n=1}^N [M(OH)_n]$$

This value of $[H_h]$ is incorporated in the hydrogen balance equation to calculate a new set of $[C_L]$. This is then used to calculate new values for \bar{n} and revised values for the terms in the equation for U. Fresh values of β_1 and β_2 are calculated from the equation for the error sum of squares (S) by the method of least squares. This process is continued until consistent results are obtained.

Results and Discussion

The dissociation constants for the ligands determined were 2.95×10^{-4} , 2.82×10^{-5} and 1.91×10^{-5} for formic, acetic and propionic acids respectively. These values are in general agreement with the corresponding values available in literature^{4,17,18}.

From the formation curves (plotted with \bar{n} against pL i.e., $-\log[L]$) for the metal ligand complexes obtained in the present studies, it was found that only mononuclear complexes were formed in all the systems studied⁷. The maximum number of complexes formed was found to be two. A typical formation curve is shown in Fig. 2. The stability constants were calculated using the experimental points which constituted the formation curves. The weighted least squares calculations using the experimental points were done ignoring the hydrolysis of the metal ion and also by incorporating the hydrolysis correction. The stability constant values obtained for the complexes with and without the hydrolysis correction are given in Table 1. It can

be seen from this table that the stability constants of the complexes of samarium(III) are not significantly affected by the hydrolysis correction. However, in the case of plutonium(III) complexes, the hydrolysis correction was found to affect the stability constant values to a very significant extent. In the case of plutonium(III)-acetate complexes it was found that after the hydrolysis correction, the data could be fitted only for the presence of a single complex in place of two complexes indicated in the calculation ignoring the hydrolysis of plutonium(III). The formation curve obtained after the hydrolysis correction is also shown in Fig. 2 for comparison. Before the hydrolysis correction, the stability constants of plutonium(III) complexes were corrected for the complexing of plutonium(III) by the iodide ion added in the form of HI, the holding reductant. This correction was done following a procedure similar to that adopted for the hydrolysis correction. It was seen that the correction due to the iodide complexing of plutonium(III) changed the

Fig. 2. Formation curves with and without hydrolysis correction-Plutonium (III)-Acetate System.

TABLE 1 - STABILITY CONSTANT VALUES OBTAINED IN THE PRESENT WORK BY WEIGHTED LEAST SQUARES METHOD

Metal ion	Ligand ion	Before correction		After hydrolysis correction	
		β_1	β_2	β_1	β_2
Plutonium (III)	Formate	35.3 ± 7.8	—	27.8 ± 7.0	—
"	Acetate	315.2 ± 22.3	$2.6 \pm 0.8 \times 10^4$	251.7 ± 26.1	—
"	Propionate	626.9 ± 65.9	$2.7 \pm 0.4 \times 10^5$	596.3 ± 65.2	$2.7 \pm 0.4 \times 10^5$
Samarium (III)	Formate	16.2 ± 0.4	33.3 ± 6.3	16.2 ± 0.4	33.3 ± 6.3
"	Acetate	100.2 ± 2.0	$2.3 \pm 0.1 \times 10^3$	100.2 ± 2.0	$2.3 \pm 0.1 \times 10^3$
"	Propionate	95.4 ± 2.4	$1.8 \pm 0.1 \times 10^3$	95.4 ± 2.4	$1.8 \pm 0.1 \times 10^3$

stability constant values only to a very small extent. The stability constant value for the first plutonium(III)-iodide complex used for this correction was taken from the work reported by Khopkar and Mathur at 30^o1^o.

The stability constants of plutonium(III)-formate and propionate complexes and those of samarium(III)-formate complexes are being reported for the first time. The stability constants of the complexes studied were found to follow the trend expected from the pK_a values of the ligands, except in the case of samarium(III)-propionate complexes. The reason for the discrepancy shown by Sm(III)-propionate complexes is not known. However, similar trend has been observed by some earlier workers also^{20,21}. It can be seen from Table 1 that the stability constants of plutonium(III) complexes are much higher than the corresponding values for samarium(III) complexes. This trend is attributed to the greater participation of 5f electrons in bond formation in plutonium(III) as compared to the 4f electrons in samarium(III). This observation is in keeping with similar results obtained by earlier authors^{2,22,23}.

The present work has used the weighted least squares calculation in which all data together are used for the calculation of stability constants unlike in many other earlier studies²⁴. The results from the present study showed that the stability constants of the plutonium(III) complexes are significantly influenced by the hydrolysis correction. This indicates the importance of hydrolysis correction in the stability constant calculation when the pH titration method is employed.

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Note—The Fortran computer program used for the above calculations is available with the authors. The same can be made available to those who wish to use it, on request.

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